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Research Article

**PREVALENCE AND RISK FACTOR OF SCABIES IN
PAKISTAN****Dr Muhammad Ansab Shah¹, Dr Atofah Ghazanfar¹,
Dr Muhammad Shoaib Afzal Khan¹**¹SIMS, Lahore**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Scabies is a neglected contagious skin disease caused by the microscopic mite, *Sarcoptes scabiei* var. *hominis*. **Aims and objectives:** The basic aim of the study is to analyse the prevalence and risk factor of scabies in Pakistan. **Material and methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted in SIMS, Lahore during January 2019 to October 2019. Diagnosis of scabies is confirmed on the presence of burrows, extraction of mite or egg from burrow at the typical site of lesion. In this study diagnosis was made on the presence of active burrows or those transformed into lesions due to secondary bacterial infection or excessive rash (rubbing). **Results:** The data was collected from 70 patients. Age of patients ranged from 17 to 49 [mean 29.17 (SD 7.13)] years and that of controls ranged from 17 to 50 [mean 29.19 (SD 7.27)] years. Level of education was matriculation (10 years of education) or lower in 27 (86.5%) patients and 13 (66.5%) controls. Out of 70 patients, 30 (90.0%) were living in dormitories of the unit barracks; the corresponding number for controls was 14 (74.5%). We arbitrarily considered family size as large when the number of individuals living in a house or dormitory was > 10; 80 (40%) patients and 28 (42.5%) controls were from large families. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that the high prevalence of scabies in the study area calls for programs to control this neglected disease and public health problem in the general population, with a special attention to poor communities.

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INTRODUCTION:

Scabies is a neglected contagious skin disease caused by the microscopic mite, *Sarcoptes scabiei* var. *hominis*. The condition is worldwide distributed with an estimated incidence of 300 million cases per year [1]. Scabietic patients characteristically suffer from intense pruritus and scratching which occasionally lead to hyperkeratosis forms and secondary bacterial skin lesions [1]. The worse itching at night due to nocturnal activity of mites causes insomnia and restlessness which has negative impact on daily regular activities of patients [2]. The psychological complications due to shameful perception of this disease discourage affected individuals to seek medical attention and inform close contacts which should be also treated to ensure eradication. The most effective means of transmission is direct skin to skin contact however indirect transmission via fomites is also effective especially in case of crusted scabies.

Scabies is a neglected parasitic disease that is a major public health problem worldwide, and particularly in resource-poor regions. It affects people of all age groups, races and socioeconomic levels. Approximately 300 million cases are reported worldwide each year [3]. Scabies causes substantial morbidity because of unbearable itch, secondary infection, post-infective complications such as glomerulonephritis [4], and the high risk of spreading the infestation to close contacts.

Scabies is caused by *Sarcoptes scabiei* var. *hominis*. The characteristic clinical feature is intense nocturnal pruritus [5]. Diagnosis is made clinically, based on patient history and physical examination. It is confirmed by the demonstration of mites, eggs, or scybala (black or brown football-shaped masses of scabies faeces) on microscopic examination [6]. Treatment includes topical or oral administration of a scabicide, an antipruritic agent such as an antihistamine, and an appropriate antimicrobial agent if secondarily infected. Multiple factors like overcrowding, poor public health education [1], sleeping habits, over-crowded sleeping space, sharing of clothes, sharing of towels, incorrect

hygiene practices and travel have frequently been cited as risk factors for scabies throughout the world.

Aims and objectives

The basic aim of the study is to analyse the prevalence and risk factor of scabies in Pakistan.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted in SIMS, Lahore during January 2019 to October 2019. Diagnosis of scabies is confirmed on the presence of burrows, extraction of mite or egg from burrow at the typical site of lesion. In this study diagnosis was made on the presence of active burrows or those transformed into lesions due to secondary bacterial infection or excessive rash (rubbing). In an attempt to obtain *Sarcoptes scabiei*, a number of smears were made both from the school children and general population. For preparation of smear following method was adopted. A burrow was opened with a straight cutting surgical needle and then scrapped longitudinally with a sharp border of a lancet. The material thus obtained was mounted on a glass slide with a drop of mounted media (KOH + Glycerin 1:1) and examined under low power microscope. A total of 70 slides were examined.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 70 patients. Age of patients ranged from 17 to 49 [mean 29.17 (SD 7.13)] years and that of controls ranged from 17 to 50 [mean 29.19 (SD 7.27)] years. Level of education was matriculation (10 years of education) or lower in 27 (86.5%) patients and 13 (66.5%) controls. Out of 70 patients, 30 (90.0%) were living in dormitories of the unit barracks; the corresponding number for controls was 14 (74.5%). We arbitrarily considered family size as large when the number of individuals living in a house or dormitory was > 10; 80 (40%) patients and 28 (42.5%) controls were from large families.

Univariate analysis showed that itching in the family, infrequent bathing, and infrequent changing of clothes, low education, residing in unit barracks and going on leave or temporary duty away from place of permanent duty were factors significantly associated with having scabies.

Table 01: Risk factor of scabies among selected population

Variables	Scabies		COR with 95% CI	AOR with 95% CI
	Yes	No		
Location				
Urban	31	226	1	
Rural	15	222	2.03 (1.07, 3.86)	2.99 (1.33, 6.71)**
Education				
Illiterate	31	236	1.86 (0.98, 3.53)	0.88 (0.39, 1.98)
Literate	15	212	1	
Frequency of bath				
At least once per week	35	415	1	
Rarely	11	33	3.95 (1.84, 8.49)	3.54 (1.36, 9.25)*
Sleeping place				
On bed	42	437	1	
On floor	4	11	3.78 (1.15, 12.40)	2.12 (0.52, 8.65)
Ever had contact with a person with itching symptom				
Yes	25	96	4.36 (2.34, 8.14)	2.66 (1.21, 5.83)*
No	21	373	1	
Family member with itchy signs				
Yes	25	29	5.56 (2.96, 10.43)	4.76 (2.20, 10.28)***
No	21	369	1	
Frequently used hand washing material				
Water only	15	48	4.03 (2.03, 8.00)	4.38(1.78, 10.76)*
Water and soap/ash/endod	31	400	1	

DISCUSSION:

Scabies is a common, though relatively neglected, parasitic skin disease of resource-poor rural and urban communities in the developing world. No or little seasonal difference was found in study areas with less contrasted climate. Crowding may also justify the higher prevalence of scabies in urban vs rural patients, which is consistent with findings in Brazil, where scabies was twice as prevalent in a densely populated urban slum as in a rural community where families lived in larger spaces [2]. In contrast, prevalence was higher in rural vs urban settings in Poland, due to lower social and material status of the rural communities and their hampered access to the medical services. Infection in close contacts was by far the single most significant risk factor, suggesting that the large majority of scabietic patients were directly or indirectly (via fomites) infected by other family members and/or housemates. Coupled with the high prevalence of the disease in the studied population, it calls for the necessity of fomite precautions and of treatment of asymptomatic family members and physical contacts of all cases of scabies [7]. And the awareness still to raise on its principal transmission patterns. Interestingly, a recent interview study amongst general medical practitioners (GMPs) in Pakistan have demonstrated a diffuse “lack of knowledge regarding various aspects of scabies” and

recommended an active intervention to improve their awareness, so that scabies will be identified and treated appropriately and valuable information will be provided to patients and communities [8,9]. The complex relationships between low socioeconomic status, overcrowding, risk behaviour, proportion of individuals infested, and the spread of *S. scabiei* in the developing world have been clearly addressed in the recent literature [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that the high prevalence of scabies in the study area calls for programs to control this neglected disease and public health problem in the general population, with a special attention to poor communities.

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